

Effect Of Vitamin D Supplementation in Diabetic Retinopathy

Mohammed Ather^{1*}, Mahammad Jubair S.², Farha Jabeen³, G. Udayasree³, T. S. Ushasree⁴, Mirza Mujtaba Ali Baig⁵

¹Professor of Ophthalmology, Bhaskar medical College Yenkapalli, Moinabad, RR district, Telangana, India

²Assistant Professor of Pharmacology, Government Medical College, Paderu Alluri Seeta Rama Raju district, AP, India

³Associate Professor of Ophthalmology, Bhaskar medical College Yenkapalli, Moinabad, RR district, Telangana, India

⁴Professor of Pharmacology, Malla Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Malla Reddy University, Dulapally, Hyderabad

⁵Senior Resident of Ophthalmology, Govt. Medical College, Mahboob nagar. Telangana, India

ABSTRACT

Aim: To study effect of Vitamin D supplementation in Diabetic Retinopathy. **Materials and Methods:** This is a Prospective, Interventional, Case control study conducted at a Tertiary eye care Hospital. 50 patients of Type 2 diabetes mellitus of both sex between 35-65 age group who were having Diabetes Retinopathy changes of Mild, Moderate and Severe NPDR were selected for study. 29 were males and 21 were females. Patients above 65 years and below 35 years Type 1 Diabetes, Pregnant women, Alcoholics, smokers, Hypertensives, Patients with Dyslipidemia and Malabsorption and crrhotics were excluded from the study. Informed consent was obtained from all patients. All Patients were examined by an experienced Ophthalmologist using Snellen's chart, Slit lamp, 90D biomicroscopy to examine fundus. Baseline investigations like FBS, PLBS, HbA1c, and estimation of Serum Vitamin D was done. Patients were divided into two groups A and B. Group A consists of 25 patients, 18 were males and 7 were females, who were having Serum levels of Vitamin D of > 20nmol/ml to < 30nmols/ml. Group B consists of 25 patients, 14 were males and 11 females, who were having < 20 nmol/ml. of Serum Vitamin D. Diabetic medication was continued in both groups. Group B was given Vitamin D supplementation. Oral 50,000 IU every week for 8 weeks and maintenance dose of 1500 IU of Vitamin D orally for 12 months. FBS, PLBS, Hb A1C and Serum Vitamin D was examined in both groups at 0 day, 6 months and 12 months. Fundus examination was done in all cases of both groups at the end of 12 months. **Results:** At the end of 12 months Group A cases showed changes in Fundus picture of 8 cases. 5 had shown progression from Moderate to severe form of NPDR. 3 cases shown progression from Severe NPDR to PDR. Whereas in Group B who received Vitamin D supplementation there was no change in Fundus picture. **Conclusion:** Vitamin D supplementation prevent Progression of NPDR to Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy.

Keywords: FBS(Fasting blood sugar), PLBS (Post Lunch Blood Sugar), HbA1C, Type 2 diabetes Mellitus, NPDR (Non proliferative diabetic Retinopathy), PDR (Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy).

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases in which there are high blood sugar levels over a prolonged period. If left untreated, diabetes can cause many complications, Diabetic Keto acidosis, Diabetic Neuropathy, Diabetic Nephropathy, Diabetic retinopathy, Diabetic Foot ulcers¹.

A recent pooled analysis from 35 population-based studies estimated that 93 million people worldwide have diabetic retinopathy, of whom 17 million have proliferative DR, 21 million have diabetic macular edema (DME), and 28 million have sight-threatening DR². Among people with diabetes, this translates to an overall prevalence of 34.6% for any DR, 7.0% for

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

proliferative DR, 6.8% for DME, and 10.2% for sight-threatening DR²

The prevalence of retinopathy is higher in people with long duration of diabetes, those with type 1 diabetes, and those with increased levels of HbA1c, blood pressure, or cholesterol¹. Historically, DR was considered to be relatively infrequent in developing countries such as now have as much, or more, DR than fully developed countries³

India is set to emerge as the diabetic capital of the world. According to the WHO, 31.7 million people were affected by diabetes mellitus (DM) in India in the year 2000. This figure is estimated to rise to 79.4 million by 2030, the largest number in any nation in the world. Almost two-third of all Type 2 and almost all Type 1 diabetics are expected to develop diabetic retinopathy (DR) over a period of time^{4,5,6}.

Vitamin D is essential for a vast number of physiologic processes and vitamin D insufficiency has reached pandemic proportions, with more than half the world's population at risk⁷. Vitamin D insufficiency has been implicated in the development of diabetes and its complications like Diabetic retinopathy.

Vitamin D may play a role in the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy through its effects on the immune system and on angiogenesis. Vitamin D exerts an anti-inflammatory effect by decreasing the proliferation of lymphocytes, natural killer cells, and several pro-inflammatory cytokines⁸. Additionally, it has been shown that the active metabolite of vitamin D, calcitriol, is a potent inhibitor of retinal neovascularization in a mouse oxygen-induced ischemic retinopathy model⁸.

Vitamin-D deficiency is also one of the important risk factor for diabetic retinopathy as vitamin-D deficiency causes inflammatory and angiogenic effects in retina.

Purpose of this study is to see the effect of Vitamin D supplementation in Diabetic retinopathy and Glycemic control of the patients.

Materials and Methods: This is a Prospective, Interventional, Case control study conducted at a

Tertiary eye care Hospital. 50 patients of Type 2 diabetes mellitus of both sex between 35-65 age group who were having Diabetic Retinopathy changes of Mild, Moderate and Severe NPDR were selected for study. 29 were males and 21 were females.

Patients above 65 years and below 35 years, Patients with Type 1 diabetes, patients with PDR, Pregnant, Smokers and Alcoholics, patients with Dyslipaemia, Mal absorption and cirrhotics were excluded from the study.

Informed consent was obtained from all patients. All Patients were examined by an experienced Ophthalmologist using Snellen's chart, Slit lamp, 90D biomicroscopy to examine fundus. Baseline investigations like FBS, PLBS, HbA1c, and estimation of Serum Vitamin D was done. Patients were divided into two groups A and B. Group A consists of 25 patients, 18 males and 7 females, who were having Serum levels of Vitamin D of >20 nmol to <30nmols/ml. Group B consists of 25 patients, 14 were males and 11 females, who were having < 20 nmol/ml. of Serum Vitamin D. Diabetic medication was continued in both groups. Group B was given Vitamin D supplementation. Oral 50,000 IU every week for 8 weeks and maintenance dose of 1500 IU of Vitamin D orally for 12 months. FBS, PLBS, Hb A1C and Serum Vitamin D was examined in both groups at 0 day, 6 months and 12 months. Fundus examination was done in all cases of both groups at the end of 12 months.

RESULTS:

Mean FBS on day 0 was 133.24mg/dl, at 6th month it was 126.44 mg/dl, and 120.52 mg/dl in group A. In group B at day 0 142.22 mg/dl, at 6th month it was 134.04 mg/dl and 120.27 mg/dl at the end of 12 months. Though there is effect on glycemic control at the end of 12 months but it occurred in both the groups. So it shows there is no additional effect of Vitamin D.

Mean PLBS on day 0 was 202.8 mg/dl, at the end of 6th month it was 184.04mg/dl and 164.68mg/dl after 12 months in Group a. whereas in Group B at day 0 mean PLBS was 203.04 mg/dl, at the end of 6th month it was 189.63 mg/dl and at the end of 12 months it

was 162.95 mg/dl. Same effect was shown with PLBS also in both groups.

Mean HbA1C was 7.92 at day 0, at the end of 6th month it was 6.86 and at the end of 12 months it was 6.62 in Group A. Whereas in Group B at day 0 it was 8.29, at the end of 6th month it was 7.81 and at the end of 12 months it was 7.13. The changes in FBS, PLBS and HbA1C was seen in both groups. It shows that Vitamin D supplementation does not have effect on Glycemic control.

Mean Serum Vitamin D levels at the end of 12 months in the Group A it was 34.6 nmol/ml showing no change from day 0 level which was 33,88 nmol/ml.

Mean serum Vitamin D levels at the end of 12 months in the Group B was 34.07 nmol/ml when compared to the values on day 0 which was 14.08 nmol/ml. There is statistical significance with p value of <0.0001.

Fundus examination of both groups was done. In Group A 8 cases showed fundus changes. 5 cases showed Progression from moderate to Severe NPDR changes. 3 cases showed progression from Severe NPDR to PDR

Whereas in group B there was no changes in Fundus findings.

Discussion: Study conducted by Dinesh R B et al⁹ shows the relationship between Vitamin D

deficiency and diabetes retinopathy in Adults Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

John Payne et al¹⁰ showed that Diabetic retinopathy patient with Type 2 Diabetes have Vitamin deficiency. Aksoy et al¹¹ had shown severity of Diabetic Retinopathy is inversely proportionate to Vitamin D deficiency.

Rani Sujatha, Ranjitha K C et al¹² had shown that Vitamin D supplementation in Type 2 DM with DR there was no Progression from NPDR to PDR. Whereas in controls who were not given supplement there was progression to PDR.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that supplementation of Vitamin D Prevents Progression from NPDR to PDR in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus with Diabetic Retinopathy

Financial support: Nil

Conflict of interest: None

Institutional Ethics committee approval obtained

REFERENCES

1. "About diabetes". World Health Organization. Retrieved 4 April 2014.
2. Yau J W, Rogers, Kawasaki et al, Global Prevalence and major risk factors of DR, Diabetes care 2012, Vol.2, \$: pg:2337-2340.
3. Zheng Y, He M, Congdon N. The worldwide epidemic of diabetic retinopathy. Indian journal of ophthalmology 2012;60(5):428-31 10.4103/0301-4738.100542.
4. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes: Estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. Diabetes Care 2004;27:1047-53.
5. Prevention of Blindness from Diabetic Retinopathy. Report of a WHO Consultation, Geneva; November, 2005.
6. Guidelines for the Comprehensive Management of Diabetic Retinopathy in India. A VISION2020 the Right to Sight India Publication; July, 2008.
7. Palomer X, Gonzalez-Clemente JM, Blanco-Vaca F, Mauricio D. Role of vitamin D in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diabetes Obes Metab. 2008;10:185–197.
8. Albert DM, Scheef EA, Wang S, et al. Calcitriol is a potent inhibitor of retinal neovascularization. Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci. 2007;48:2327–2334.
9. Dinesh R b, R Anil Kumar et al, Vitamin D and Diabetic Retinopathy in Indian adults with type2 DM, International Journal of Medical research and review, 2018;6(04):221-227
10. John F.Payne, Robin Ray et al, Vitamin D Insufficiency in DR, Endocrine practice, vol18, Issue 2, March- April pages 185-193
11. Aksoy et al, Severity of DR is inversely proportionate to Vitamin D deficiency, Ophthalmology, 2018, Vol12, issue2, pg230-240.

12. Rani Sujatha, Ranjitha K C et al, A clinical study of VitaminD supplementation in DR patients with Type 2 DM, IJOOO,7(1),64-67

HOW TO CITE: Mohammed Ather*, Mahammad Jubair S., Farha Jabeen, G. Udayasree, T. S. Ushasree, Mirza Mujtaba Ali Baig, Effect Of Vitamin D Supplementation In Diabetic Retinopathy, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (1), 1068-1071. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18311010>

